

EBFMC25-OP-37 · Acute Occipital Lobe Infarction in a Patient Presenting with Complaint of Decreased Vision

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Homonymous hemianopia (HH) may occur due to pathologies involving posterior visual pathways, such as ischemia or infarction of the occipital cortex.

Case Presentation: Detection of visual field defects plays a key role in the early diagnosis and management of many potentially life-threatening conditions.

Discussion: HH may impair daily activities such as driving or reading and can lead to decreased vision. Thus, patients may have difficulty describing their visual field defects.

Conclusion: The confrontation test is the most frequently used and easily applicable screening tool for assessing visual field defects in the presence of HH.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Homonymous hemianopia, confrontation, visual field

INTRODUCTION

Homonymous hemianopia (HH) or homonymous hemianopsia is a visual field defect characterized by loss of vision occurring in the same half of the visual field in both eyes. Pathologies involving the posterior visual pathways can cause homonymous hemianopia (HH). Among these pathologies, occipital cortex ischemia or infarction is the most common cause, accounting for approximately 75% of cases; however, lesions involving the optic tract and optic radiations have also been reported to result in HH (Kedar et al., 2007). In a study by Zhang et al. involving 904 cases, HH showed nearly equal gender distribution (male 52%, female 48%) with a mean patient age around 50 years (Zhang et al., 2006). Detection of visual field defects has a significant impact on the early diagnosis and management of various diseases. The confrontation test is the most frequently used screening method for evaluating visual field defects in the presence of HH. Another option is automated or manual (Goldmann, tangent screen, Humphrey visual field) perimetry testing (Ruia & Tripathy, 2023). In this study, we present a case of acute occipital lobe infarction detected in a patient who presented to the ophthalmology outpatient clinic with a complaint of decreased vision. The confrontation test was initially used as a screening method, raising suspicion of right homonymous hemianopia. Following confirmation with Humphrey visual field testing, subsequent cranial imaging revealed acute occipital lobe infarction.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 70-year-old male patient presented to the ophthalmology clinic with complaints of bilateral visual deterioration lasting for two days. Clinically, the patient was partially uncooperative and poorly compliant with examination. Visual acuity (VA) was 0.6 in both eyes. During confrontation testing, the patient showed no object tracking on the right side. Intraocular pressure (IOP) was measured as 17 mmHg in the right eye and 18 mmHg in the left eye. Anterior segment examination revealed normal conjunctiva, clear cornea, and normal anterior chamber in both eyes. Fundus examination showed bilateral optic discs and retinas to be normal. Spectral domain optical coherence tomography (SD-OCT) findings were unremarkable. Humphrey visual field testing revealed right homonymous hemianopia (Figure 1).

Figure 1

Cranial imaging was performed due to suspected acute cerebrovascular event. Cranial tomography (CT) showed an acute cerebral infarction in the left occipital lobe paramedian region (Figure 2). The patient was urgently referred to the neurology clinic for acute cerebral infarction management.

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